

SEO in Digital Marketing

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Abstract

This paper explains about the role of Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) in digital marketing. This paper breaks the thought of people that the digital marketing simply means marketing which is done through online websites like Flipkart, Snapdeal etc. It proves that marketing has a wide scope and is just isn't about meeting people face to face and convince them your product is good but to provide the people with what they actually need. There will always be an advantage and disadvantage for each and every thing in a person's point of view. This paper also summarises the pros and cons of SEO in digital marketing. It also briefly explains about the current scenario of SEO and the jobs that are available for them. It includes some of the other digital marketing types such as PPC and Social Media Marketing.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing means the marketing the products or services using digital channel to reach consumers. It doesn't only include famous websites Flipkart, Snapdeal etc. There are a lot of other platforms which does this kind of marketing. They maybe websites, social media, Youtube, Facebook, Instagram and so on. Digital marketing also goes beyond internet marketing that does not use internet. The most important factor about digital marketing is that the Time is saved a lot when it is compared to face to face marketing. All the information about the products are easily accessed through websites and product reviews are also given by many Youtubers.

Search Engine Optimisation (Seo)

Search Engine Optimisation is the process of affecting the online visibility of a website in a web search engine's unpaid results which is referred to as "organic" results. It means the website which appears on top of the search engine after the keywords have been searched. The people who search these results may become customers. Some people think that there is only one search engine which is Google. Because the word googling has become a verb for searching something on the internet. There are many other top search engines such as Bing, Yahoo, Ask.com, AOL.com, Baidu, Wolframalpha, Duckduck go etc.

To rank top on the search list the owner of a website or a blog whichever he want to get it to the top need to make sure that the website he owns should be neat and properly arranged. Search engines is being run on an algorithm where various factors affect the search of a particular person. The content should be understandable to the algorithm and more importantly the links connected to the website must be user friendly.

Role of Seo in Digital Marketing

Search engine optimisation is the process of making a website crawl on top of the website above all the other websites. A survey says that nearly 14 billion searches are done in a month. To be on top of this list a fair knowledge about SEO is required. For any business advertising is of utmost need. When a business goes online advertising works best to assemble a huge amount of web traffic. SEO gives us a great opportunity for a great deal of free advertising. There is a common belief that people will check out the first two search results of the Search Engine Result Page. There are few elements which builds up the quality of the website to top on the SERP. They are as follows:

- Website names and URLs
- Page content
- Meta tags
- Characteristics of Link
- Usability and accessibility
- Page design

Process of Seo

Crawling

Every search engine has this software known as crawler. It crawls the web page content. The crawler won't see each and every page daily or whether it is being updated. It is important to know what the crawler can search. There are some things which the crawlers will not search they are images, flash movies, Java scripts, frames, password protected pages and directories. Those which are not viewable or not spidered. So if we want to sell something through a website then it shouldn't contain much of the above so that the visitor will find it easy to access the site.

Indexing

After crawling the spider stores the data in a giant database where it can be retrieved after a keyword has been searched. If the search engine cannot understand the page content then it won't be displayed in SERP. So it is important to optimise the page content.

Search Request

There will be millions of websites having the same content. But to top the SERP the page content should be relevant to the keyword search. If we have irrelevant content in that page i.e something distorts the purpose of the web page then it won't appear in the search list.

Algorithms

A search engine algorithm takes the keyword search sorts through the record of sites which it has indexed and reverts the page which has relevant information relating to the keyword search. There are three types of algorithms On - site, Off - site, Whole - site algorithms. Each algorithm looks at various aspects such as meta tags, title tags, keywords etc. Each search engine has it's own algorithm. That's why the results differ for the same keyword in various search engines.

Retrieving

After all this above process. The end results will be visible in the search results.

Changing Scenario

The personal reputation is becoming more and more important. The way the SEO works has been changing time to time. Old school of link building has some improvisations. Content related searches is now being converted into inbound quality links which affects SEO. Now there are ways to earn money through shortening the links. But some links will only appear as spams.

Seo Strategy

Target Market

Before getting into improvement of your websites you have to build a strategy. First of it is to make sure what kind of customers that we are going to deal with or to whom we are going to sell our products. Google analytics will help you in your investigations on these factors.

Mobile Friendly Approaches

The website should be mobile friendly as a survey says that mobile searches has exceeded desktop searches. People are searching through mobiles than in desktops because of it's compatibility. We can know whether our website is mobile friendly or not through Google's mobile friendly tester.

Keywords

Keywords are the most important in SEO. It determines the Return on Investment. A SEO expert will spend a long time deciding the keywords to get maximum visitors.

More Search Engines

The website should not perform well in just one search engine. It should perform in other search engines also. It can be done by studying about the search algorithms of different search engines.

Social Media Linking

The websites should be linked to the social media sites like Facebook, Instagram etc. to keep the customers updated about what is happening in the company.

Seo Pros and Cons

Pros

You will have a free flow of traffic. Unlike PPC which requires considerable amount of investment SEO needs expertise which will definitely result in the increase of traffic to the site. SEO has to ability to expand your business and increases your sales than posting normal ads about your website. It's why SEO is linked to investing in real estate and it can give you a large amount of return on investment if you get it right. Once you get your site n top of the SERP then your brand will have popularity. If we try to do this through PPC then many people has ad - blocker which won't let them view our site.

People will have access to data and the result will be ever lasting. It won't fade away just because we don't pay for it. If we keep up with the changing trends and the search engine algorithm then we will still be on top. SEO can make you stand out among 1 billion websites on the web. World wide web is one of the largest incipient markets in the World economy which allows even small business enter great heights. The relationship between SEO and social media is by - directional.

Cons

It takes a lot of time for SEO to show results. It may even take hours, days or weeks. It is because some search engine's algorithms changes frequently. So the search results will not be consistent. Because of this it will take a long time to get ROI. This will not be suitable for independent companies which depend their income totally from this.

To enter into the competitive world it requires a lot of investment. SEO experts need to hired to carry out these tasks and to stay updated. The important disadvantage of SEO is that there is no assurance that this will work. Even though we have optimised our website about all the keywords,

phrases, relevancy there is no assurance that the web page will top the list. There is a possibility that all the efforts may go to waste when the search engines release unpredictable updates. The marketer will have no idea what to do after all his efforts gone south.

Pay Per Click Marketing

PPC is a model of internet marketing where the advertiser will pay a fee when each one of their ads are clicked. It is a way of buying the visits to your website instead of people visiting the websites automatically. Sometimes a pay is worth it because when we have to pay 4 Rs. a click but will get a sale of 400Rs. then we have made a fortune.

Social Media Marketing

It is the way of promoting the product by way of using the social media platforms. One of the reasons why this type of marketing can give us a good fortune is that a person uses at least 100 minutes a day on social media. So there are a lot of possibilities to spread awareness about the products which we want to sell. The trend of modern age is that if you don't have a social media account you don't exist in this world so it is mandatory for every marketer to have a social media account to improve the sales.

Now a days people are selling products even on Youtube. Same products can be sold anyone but the real question how to get on the top of the list so that people will see what we offer. Youtube Tags play an important role in this case. Hashtags can also be included. Sometimes people will add tags which are irrelevant but are in trending to make them see what their channel is offering.

Current Scenario

India has a very large population and with the introduction of the internet it has become the country which has the largest number of internet users in the world. Looking at the current scenario people in India not only grown in the search queries but also the people who implement the awareness they get from the internet.

2018 will be a great year for SEO. SERP is about to get new features. Structured data is a way of HTML that uses a specific vocabulary, explaining the search engines how to interpret the content. The famous search engine Google will now load in three seconds. Better relevancy will be introduced in search engines. There is a common belief that video and image searches will commonly improve.

Like the famous entrepreneur Gary Vee said "life shrinks and expands on the proportion of your willingness to take risks and try new things."

Conclusion

SEO is now the need of any company which focuses to sell its product online. But any means of dishonesty to rank on the top of the SERP will result in the banning of the website. So this modern era which is based on internet requires lot of expertise to satisfy the need of the customer. Having incorporated all these a digital marketing strategy with a balanced SEO moves will definitely give you a good ROI.

Web Sites

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